

A Study of Pap Smear in a Tertiary Care Hospital in South AssamSuborna Bhattacharjee¹, Soumistha Das², Monoj Kumar Deka³, Arindam Das⁴,
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Abstract:

Background: Cervical cancer is one of the leading causes of mortality among women worldwide. However, cervical cancer is preventable, if detected at an early (preinvasive) stage. Pap smear test is a very important, simple, non-invasive and cost effective test for assessing female reproductive health by early detection of any cervical abnormality. Hence, this study was carried out with an aim to study the spectrum of cervical smears (obtained through Pap smear) in females aged 21-65 years.

Materials and Methods: This hospital based prospective study was carried out for a period of one year at Silchar Medical College and Hospital. Pap smears (conventional method) were collected from 100 women, aged between 21 and 65 years, attending gynaecology OPD with various complaints, after obtaining their consent. The smears were immediately fixed with 95% ethyl alcohol, stained and later reported according to Bethesda system (2014) in the Department of Pathology, S.M.C.H. Pregnant women and other women who did not give consent were excluded from the study.

Results: 86.7 % of the Pap smears were reported as NILM. 5% of the smears were unsatisfactory for evaluation while 1.7% showed ASCUS, 2.5% showed LSIL, 1.7% showed HSIL and the remaining 0.83% showed SCC.

Conclusion: Pap smear is a simple, non-invasive and cost-effective method for detecting pre-cancerous lesions of cervix and thus helps in preventing the development of invasive malignancies. It can thus be established as a routine screening procedure to reduce the burden of cervical morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: Cancer cervix; Pap smear; Bethesda system; LSIL; HSIL; NILM.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer is one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality among women worldwide. Infact, cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer among women around the globe after breast, colorectal and lung cancer.[1]According to recent W.H.O. statistics, the estimated number of new cases and deaths in 2022 were 660 000 and 350 000 respectively. The highest rates of incidence and mortality were seen in low- and middle- income countries. [2] Fortunately, cervical cancer is preventable, if detected at an early (preinvasive) stage. A long preinvasive stage makes cervical cancer amenable to screening and treatment as long as it is detected early and managed effectively.

Evidences show that majority of cervical cancers can be attributed to infection by high risk Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) [3]. HPV is a double stranded DNA virus that infects skin and mucosal cells, including anogenital region and oral cavity. It

can be transmitted easily via sexual intercourse and direct contact. There are more than 100 types of HPV in nature, of which 12 are considered to be of high risk and having oncogenic potential. Of these, HPV 16 and 18 combined are thought to account for almost 70% of cervical cancers.[4]

Pap smear is a very simple, safe and cost effective diagnostic tool for assessing cervical health in women, i.e. for detecting abnormal, atypical cells in cervix. This Papanicolaou test, more commonly known as Pap test or Pap smear, was developed by Georgios Papanicolaou in 1940s .This Papanicolaou test has remained the mainstay of cervical cancer screening for more than seven decades now. [3,4]. Several studies have demonstrated that more than 75% of new HPV infection occurs in adolescents and young adults. This may be due to the lack of adaptive immune responses or relatively large area of cervical epithelium undergoing squamous

metaplasia in this age group, which is supposed to pave the way for HPV DNA to infect the basal cell layer where it can then proliferate. A second peak (though lower) of HPV infection has been observed in older women (around 55 years age) perhaps due to waning immunity or reactivation of latent infection [5].

This hospital based prospective study was done to determine the spectrum of cervical smears in women aged 21 years to 65 years through a simple and cost-effective method of Pap smear cytology.

Materials and methods

This prospective study was carried out for a period of 1 year from May 2023 to April 2024 at the Department of Pathology in Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Silchar, Assam. A total of 120 women in the age group 21 years to 65 years attending Gynaecology outdoor (in Silchar Medical College and Hospital) with various complaints were included in the study. Pregnant women, women with active bleeding and women who did not give consent were excluded from the study.

The cervix is made up of an outer ectocervix lined by squamous epithelium and an in endocervix lined by columnar epithelium. The point where the squamous and columnar epithelium meets is called the squamocolumnar junction. Metaplasia advances from the original squamocolumnar junction inwards toward the external os outwards and this area is called the transformation zone. It is from this area that sample for Pap smear study is collected. [6,7]

At the outset, informed written consent is obtained from all the women participating in the study. The entire procedure was explained to the patients and they were instructed to abstain from sexual intercourse, or avoid using any vaginal medication or contraceptives for at least 48 hours before the sample collection. The patient was placed in lithotomy position and the cervix was visualized with the help of a sterile bivalved speculum. Both cytobrush and

Ayre's spatula was used in this study for sample collection. First the cytobrush was put into the cervix into the transformation zone and rotated through 3600 in a clockwise direction. The sample thus obtained is immediately spread on a clean glass slide.

The Ayre's spatula is then introduced into the cervix through the external os and rotated 3600 in a clockwise manner and the squamocolumnar junction is scraped. The material thus obtained is immediately spread onto a glass slide. Thus, in our study two samples were obtained from each patient. The smears thus prepared were immediately fixed using 95% ethyl alcohol and sent to the Department of Pathology of the same hospital for cytological study where the slides were stained with Pap stain following the standard protocol and later reported according to the Bethesda System, 2014.

The Bethesda System of Classification of Pap smear, 2014 categorized the findings into the following categories: Negative for intraepithelial lesion or malignancy (NILM), unsatisfactory for evaluation or inadequate sample, Atypical squamous cells (ASC) which includes Atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance (ASCUS) and ASC cannot exclude HSIL (ASC-H), atypical glandular cell (AGC), low grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (LSIL), high grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (HSIL), and carcinoma or malignant. [8]

Data was entered and analysed by using Microsoft Excel 2016.

Results

NILM was the most common cytological pattern observed accounting for 86.7% of the Pap smears. 5% of the smears were unsatisfactory for evaluation while 1.7% showed ASCUS, 2.5% showed LSIL and 1.7% showed HSIL. Malignancy was the least common pattern observed, accounting for 0.83% of cases. The results of our study have been tabulated below. (Table 1).

Table 1:

Pap report	n	%
Unsatisfactory sample	6	5
NILM	104	86.7
Normal	54	45
Inflammatory	50	41.7
ASCUS	2	1.7
LSIL	3	2.5
HSIL	2	1.7
Squamous cell carcinoma	1	0.83

Figure 1: a)NILM showing superficial squamous cells without any cytological atypia b) LSIL showing variable sized atypical cells with enlarged nuclei(40x)c)HSIL showing sheet of parabasal type cells exhibiting nuclear hyperchromasia and pleomorphism, high N/C ratio (40x)d)SCC showing parabasal-like cells with high N/C ratio, nuclear pleomorphism, irregular nuclear membranes and multiple nucleoli (40x)

Discussion

Pap smear is the foremost screening technique and a very safe and cost-effective tool for detecting precancerous lesions of cervix and carcinomatous changes of cervix. [9]

The most common Pap smear finding in the present study was NILM accounting for 86.7% of the cases. This is in accordance with earlier studies where NILM was the most reported category ranging from 68% to 96.31% [9,10,11,12]. However, this is in conflict with study conducted by Baamer et al, who found ASC-US (26.1%) to be the most common Pap smear finding. [13] The number of unsatisfactory smears in the present study was found to be 5%. This is in accordance with many previous studies where the number of unsatisfactory smears varied from 1% to 12% [9,10,11,14].

In a study conducted by Sharma et al it was observed that older age group and cervical erosions were the most common reasons for unsatisfactory conventional Pap smears. They also observed that most of the unsatisfactory smears were associated with the clinical complaints of white discharge and lower abdominal pain and thus they concluded that the unsatisfactoriness of the smears could be due to cell obscuration by mucus, inflammatory cells, blood, etc. [15] Although the rate of unsatisfactory smears is significantly reduced with Liquid Based Cytology, the factors leading to unsatisfactory smears should be borne in mind since in resource

limited countries, it is the conventional Pap smear that is most commonly used for cervical cancer screening [16]. In our study, we found that epithelial cell abnormalities were found in 0.83% to 2.5% : ASC-US – 1.7%, LSIL- 2.5%, HSIL- 1.7%, Carcinoma-0.83%. In a study conducted by Sethy et al, epithelial cell abnormality was found to 4.62 % of the satisfactory smears. [9] Kanthimathy et al found the prevalence of epithelial cell abnormalities to be 19.1% which is in conformation with the data conducted by Vafaei et al [12,17]. Verma et al, in their study found epithelial cell abnormalities in 9% cases with ASC-US=1%, LSIL=5.5%, HSIL=2.5% [14]. However, Baamer et al observed epithelial cell abnormalities in 91% cases with ASC-US being the most frequent (26.1%) and SCC being the least (0.9%). [13]

In the present study, most of the epithelial cell abnormalities were found in women above 40 years of age. This is consistent with the study conducted by Sachan et al who reported epithelial cell abnormality to be most common between the age group 40 and 60 years. [10] Sethy et al also observed that most of the epithelial cell abnormalities were present in women above 45 years of age. [9] However, Kanthimathy et al, in their study of Pap smear in high-risk group of women observed that the highest prevalence of epithelial cell abnormalities was found in women of child bearing age (less than 39 years of age). Females showing features of ASCUS and LSIL were ad-

vised to repeat Pap smear test after 6 months and if found positive on repeat smear, were advised to undergo loop electrosurgical excision procedure. Participants showing ASC-H and HSIL were advised to undergo colposcopic biopsy for confirmation and if confirmed were advised hysterectomy. [12] In our study, the most commonly reported clinical symptoms were white discharge per vagina followed by abdominal pain and post coital bleeding. This is in accordance with most of the previous studies. [9,10,13,18] We acknowledge that our study had a few limitations. First, our sample size was small which can be attributed to social stigma, shyness, lack of awareness, etc. Secondly, LBC (Liquid Based Cytology), which can help in reducing the rate of unsatisfactory smears, was not available in our institute at the time of study.

Conclusion

Pap smear is a simple, safe and cost-effective screening tool for detecting and treating early (pre-cancerous lesions) abnormalities in cervical epithelium. Infact, it should be established as a routine screening procedure as it can immensely reduce the burden of cervical cancer around the globe. The community should be made aware about the importance and necessity of routine Pap smear tests. Although LBC can serve as a better alternative to conventional Pap smears because of lower rate of unsatisfactory smears, conventional Pap smear still remains the best screening method in resource-limited settings considering its cost-effectiveness.

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